

Notes on *Leptopholcus gracilis* Berland, 1920 a leaf-dwelling spider from South Africa (Araneae: Pholcidae)

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ABSTRACT: *Leptopholcus gracilis* Berland, 1920 is a slender, long-legged pholcid spider found across eastern and southern Africa. It's a delicate, cryptic species with very few confirmed observations. It is relatively rare in collections, probably due mainly to its cryptic habits. In this paper, the general morphology is discussed with notes on their lifestyle, conservation and distribution in South Africa.

Keywords: biodiversity, distribution, iNaturalist, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), taxonomy

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Leptopholcus* Simon, 1893, represented by 22 species, is known from Africa and Asia. The six African species occur widely in sub-Saharan Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2026). Only one species, *Leptopholcus gracilis*, recorded from South Africa, was first described by Berland in 1920. It is found across East and Southern Africa, specifically in Somalia, Kenya, Tanzania, Mozambique and South Africa. They are pale pholcids with long abdomens and long, thin legs (Figs 1– 3). They are known for their leaf-dwelling adaptations. Most species appear to be restricted to relatively humid areas, where they live cryptically on large leaves. Huber (2011), in his revision of some taxa of the Pholcidae examined specimens from Mozambique and South Africa, but only assigned them tentatively to *L. gracilis*.

In this paper, the general morphology is discussed with notes on their lifestyle, conservation and distribution in South Africa.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida, 12 specimens have so far been collected during surveys in Limpopo and KwaZulu-Natal (Fig. 13), and voucher specimens are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida at the Agricultural Research Council in Pretoria (NCA) (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al., 2015).

Five additional records, mainly from KwaZulu-Natal, were obtained from research-grade observations by the public available on the iNaturalist database (Fig. 13).

TAXONOMY

Leptopholcus gracilis Berland, 1920

Leptopholcus gracilis Berland, 1920: 131 (f); Brignoli, 1980: 649 (f, Dm); Huber, 2011: 71 (mf); Dippenaar-Schoeman 2023: 106 (f).

Diagnostic characters: TL 6–7 mm. Carapace low, flattened, lacking a fovea (Fig. 2); six eyes in two widely separated triads on the margin of the carapace; anterior median eyes represented as a pair of specks between triads (Figs 2, 5–6). Carapace translucent with dark patches over the eye region (Figs 1–2). Abdomen vermiform; much longer than wide; parallel-sided; anteriorly nearly square, with round posterior margin (Figs 1–3, 7); dorsum pale green to yellowish to almost translucent; decorated with brown paired spots (Fig. 10). Legs are very long; same colour as carapace; distal tips of leg segments darkened; in some femora spotted (Fig. 12); legs without spines and curved hairs.

Figures 1–4. *Leptopholcus gracilis* female from Umhlanga, KwaZulu-Natal. Credit: Peter Webb.

Figures 5–9. *Leptopholcus gracilis*. 5–6. Eye pattern. 7. Habitus lateral view. 8. Epigyne. 9. Palp. Credits: 5–6. After Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué(1997). 8–9. After Huber(2011).

Sexual dimorphism is slight. For epigyne, see Fig. 8; for male palp, see Fig. 9 (Huber, 2011). Sexual dimorphism slight (Huber, 2011).

DISTRIBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Somalia, Kenya, Tanzania, Mozambique, Congo, São Tomé and Príncipe, Bandrélé, Mayotte Reunion, Madagascar, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA:

SANSA RECORDS (Fig. 13): KwaZulu-Natal: Bonamanzi Reserve (-32.3, 28.07); Dukuduku State Forest, Hlabisa (-28.37, 32.23); Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.1); iSimangaliso Wetland park, Hells Gate (-28.01, 32.44); iSimangaliso Wetland park, False Bay Park (-27.92, 32.27); iSimangaliso Wetland park, Kosi Bay Nature(-26.93, 32.87); Ndumo Camp Pongola River (-26.88, 32.25); Tembe Elephant Park, Sihangwana (-27.03, 32.42); Umhlanga Rocks (-29.73, 31.07). **Limpopo:** Klein Kariba (-24.88, 28.29); Kruger National Park, Pafuri (-22.46, 31.3); Rochdale farm (N slopes of Soutpansberg Mts.) (-22.54, 29.41).

INATURALIST OBSERVATIONS (Fig. 13): KwaZulu-Natal: Simangaliso Wetland Park, Emangusi (-27.41, 32.69); uMkhanyakude District (-27.90, 32.35); Paradise Valley, Pinetown(-29.83, 30.89); Tyburn Way, Westville (-29.85, 30.92); KwaMazabane (-26.95, 32.82).

Figures 10–12. *Leptopholcus gracilis*. 10. Female from Umhlanga, KZN showing the long legs. 11. Male from Westville, KZN. 12. Female with spiderlings. Credits: 10. Peter Webb. 11. Suncana Bradley. 12. Nicky Bay.

Figure 13. Map showing the distribution of *Leptopholcus gracilis* from SANSA records in the NCA (red) and research grade observations in iNaturalist (green) downloaded on 15/3/2026. Credit: Wynand Uys

HABITAT

Leptopholcus gracilis is relatively rare in collections, likely due to its cryptic habits. They appear to be restricted to relatively humid areas, as found in KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. They were mainly recorded from the Indian Coastal Belt with a few records from the Savanna Biomes (Fig. 13).

LIFESTYLE

They are cryptic leaf-dwelling spiders and live on the underside of large leaves where they spend their resting period most of the day pressed flat against the leaf surface, possibly to avoid predation (Figs 4 & 11). They hunt small arthropods and, with limited vision, they seem to rely on vibrations more than sight. No silk threads are visible in the photographs, so minimal silk is apparently used. Females build elongated egg sacs and with it in their chelicerae stay on the leaf surface on the underside.

CONSERVATION STATUS

The species has a wide distribution throughout Africa and Madagascar and therefore listed as least concern. In South Africa it has been collected from several protected areas in KwaZulu-Natal such as Hluhluwe Nature Reserve, Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad *et al.*, 2006) and Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad *et al.*, 2010) and in Limpopo in the Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy, 2003) and the Soutpansberg Mountain (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024).

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